

DEPRECIATION METHODS CONSIDERED AS FIXED ASSETS AND ADVANTAGES OF USING THEM IN SMALL BUSINESS SUBJECTS

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Annotation: The article deals with depreciation methods considered as fixed assets and advantages of using them in small business subjects. Moreover, description of depreciation, its types and main functions were highlighted.

Key words: *fixed asset, trademarks, non-cash expense, tangible assets, [salvage value](#), depreciated percentage, Double Declining Balance Method.*

Depreciation is the term we use for the loss of value of a fixed asset during its lifetime. Generally speaking, depreciation only occurs in fixed assets, such as property, vehicles, or machinery as they are tangible, physical assets that your business owns. Although both fixed assets and other intangible assets, such as trademarks or branding, show on your company's balance sheet for accounting purposes, only fixed assets are able to be depreciated for tax purposes. Depreciation in accounting refers to an indirect and explicit cost that a company incurs every year while using a fixed asset such as equipment, machinery, or expensive tools. It is the depleting value of a tangible asset.

The value of the assets gets depleted due to constant use for business purposes. Companies depreciate to account for this value throughout the useful life of that asset. It is a fixed cost for the companies, and the amount depreciated can be used to purchase new machinery after the old one turns into a scrap. Also, it is seen as a business expense despite being a non-cash expense[1]. Companies depreciate to allocate the cost of a [tangible asset](#), over

its [useful life](#). When the asset is used, wear and tear occur from erosion, dust, and decay. Despite proper maintenance and precaution, it is impossible to preserve the original form and quality of the asset. Therefore, depreciation expense is used to recognize the amount of wear and tear. Firms depreciate because the technology used in the machine may become obsolete, or the asset may become inoperable due to an accident.

In depreciation, there is no cash outflow. Instead, while accounting, this expense is transferred to the [accumulated depreciation](#). It is an essential part of accounting that facilitates companies to record the real-time [book value](#) of tangible assets. Also, this sum can be used for purchasing a new asset in the future. Now, let us understand some of the terminologies used in this concept:

- **Fixed Asset Cost:** It is the cost at which the organization buys a tangible asset.
- **Salvage Value:** The residual cost can be recovered from selling the asset after its useful life.
- **Useful Life of Fixed Asset:** It is the estimated number of years for which an asset remains productive and efficient.
- **Depreciation Rate:** It is the percentage charged as depreciation on the fixed asset.

All tangible assets depreciate with time. Therefore, firms use the following five methods to charge for it[2].

1 – Straight-Line Method (SLM)

This is the simplest method of calculating used most of the time. In SLM, a constant depreciation amount is charged every year. First, corporations have to estimate the salvage (residual) value. The [salvage value](#) represents the cost the company expects to recover at the end of the machine's useful life. After deducting this residual value from the fixed asset cost, the value acquired is divided by the useful life of the [fixed assets](#).

Straight-Line Method Formula:

$$\text{Depreciation} = \frac{(\text{Cost of Fixed Asset} - \text{Salvage Value})}{\text{Useful Life of Fixed Asset}}$$

2 – Declining Balance Method

In this method, the depreciated percentage is charged on the net book value of a fixed asset. This netbook value is the remaining balance of fixed asset cost after deducting the overall depreciation charged for the previous years. Thus, the depreciable value diminishes every year, and so does the depreciated expense.

Declining Balance Method Formula:

$$\text{Depreciation} = (\text{Net Book Value} - \text{Salvage Value}) \times \text{Rate of Depreciation}$$

#3 – Double Declining Balance Method

This method works similar to the [declining balance method](#); however, it charges double the depreciated rate on the fixed asset's balance or net book value. Therefore, it is also known as an [accelerated method](#).

Double Declining Balance Method Formula:

$$\text{Depreciation} = (\text{Net Book Value} - \text{Salvage Value}) \times \text{Rate of Depreciation} \times 2$$

#4 – Units of Production Method

Under this method, the fraction of the number of fixed asset units (machinery) produced per year and the total number of units generated in a lifetime is multiplied with the fixed asset cost to yield the depreciated expense of each year. Hence, if the production decreases, the depreciated cost also steps down and vice versa.

Units of Production Method Formula:

$$\text{Depreciation Rate Per Unit} = \frac{\text{Fixed Asset Cost} - \text{Salvage Value}}{\text{Total number of units produced during the useful life}}$$

$$\text{Depreciation} = \text{Number of units produced in a given year} \times \text{Depreciation Rate Per Unit}$$

#5 – Sum-of-Years Digits Method

As the name indicates, this method takes the total useful years. Here the digits are arranged in descending order. Then the remaining number of useful years are divided by this sum and multiplied by 100 to get the depreciated rate for the particular year. Finally, the depreciated expense is computed by multiplying this rate with the remaining fixed asset cost after deducting the salvage value[3].

Sum-of-Years Digits Method Formula:

$$\text{Depreciation} = \left[\frac{\text{Useful Life Remaining}}{\text{Sum of Years Digits}} \times 100 \right] \times \text{Depreciable Fixed Asset Value}$$

Depreciating assets impacts various financial ratios and accounting books in the following manner:

Depreciating assets significantly impacts the [Income Statement](#) and [Balance Sheet](#) of [capital-intensive firms](#). Choice of useful life and salvage value also impacts depreciating expense and the stated asset values. Assets depreciate more when they have a

shorter useful life and lower salvage values. Higher depreciation expense subdues the return ratios. An analyst should take care of this while comparing firms with different methods. Compared to SLM, the accelerated depreciating method tends to depress both net income and shareholder's equity during the initial years. Also, return ratios are lower when Accelerated methods are used, hence more conservative. The impact, however, reverses in the later years with a lower depreciating expense. A firm with high capital may take a conservative approach of adopting the Accelerated approach as depreciating less with aging assets is compensated by depreciating more on new assets. Depreciating with conservative methods also increases the [Asset Turnover Ratio](#).

The most common way of calculating depreciating expense is the straight-line method. The difference between the fixed asset cost and its salvage value is divided by the useful life of that asset in years to get the depreciating value for each year. The business entities depreciate fixed assets every year irrespective of production or sales. Fixed assets include machinery, tools, equipment, and vehicles. In accounting, therefore, depreciating of assets comes under fixed cost. However, when computed using the units of production method, it is taken as a variable cost. This is because the rise or fall in production causes the asset to depreciate more or less[4].

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that depletion in the value of something. In accounting, fixed assets' value declines every year due to wear and tear caused by constant usage. This happens throughout the useful life of an asset. Companies depreciate to account for the cost of fixed assets. After all, every asset has a specific lifespan and turns into scrap after this period. Therefore, recording the appropriate book value of an asset helps accumulate funds for its future replacement.

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